

Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 8 (0000 up to 7777)

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Inder Taneja published two papers on Zenodo (combining results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
18-01-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ²⁸
03-02-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20000 to 30000 ²⁹

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵
28-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (03) ²⁵
06-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (04) ³⁰
07-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (05) ³¹

Historic Overview

Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases ¹⁶

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 11 through 16):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (completing the base 11 up to 16 series):

Date	Title
09-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX) ²³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (extending the base 16 series):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFF) ²⁴

Authors published two papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 17 through 62):

Date	Title
23-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to #####) ²⁶
02-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 62 (0000 up to #####) ²⁷

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 7 through 9):

Date	Title
13-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 9 (0000 up to 8888) ³²
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 8 (0000 up to 7777) ³³
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 7 (0000 up to 6666) ³⁴

Base 8 Crazy Sequential Representation

For example, two valid base 8 crazy sequential representations:

27_{10}	33_8	5_{10}	5_8
$-1_8/2_8*((-3_8+4_8)^5-67_8)$		$7_8+(6_8-5_8)^4 3_8*2_8/-1_8$	

For clarity, the corresponding base 10 representations:

$-1_{10}/2_{10}*((-3_{10}+4_{10})^5-55_{10})$	$7_{10}+(6_{10}-5_{10})^4 3_{10}*2_{10}/-1_{10}$
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Definition

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	+	-	*	/	^	()
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	-----

Digits 1 up to 7 occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$-1/2*((-3+4)^5-67)$	$7+(6-5)^4 3*2/-1$
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Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$-1/2*((-3+4)^5-67)$	$7+(6-5)^4 3*2/-1$
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Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$-1/2*((-3+4)^5-67)$	$7+(6-5)^4 3*2/-1$
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Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$-1/2*((-3+4)^5-67)$	$7+(6-5)^4 3*2/-1$
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Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$-1/2*((-3+4)^5-67)$	$7+(6-5)^4 3*2/-1$
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Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$(1+2-3)*45^*(6^7)$	$76^*(5^4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*45/-(6^7)$	$76/-(5^4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*45^-(6^7)$	$76^-(5^4)*(3-2-1)$
$(-(1+2)+3)*45^(6+7)$	$76^(5+4)*(-(3-2)+1)$
$-(1^2^3*(4-5-6+7))$	$-((7-6-5+4)*3^2^1)$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Aim

Identify genuine base 8 crazy sequential representations for 0000_8 up to 7777_8

Expected number of representations = $2_8 + 7777_8 + 7777_8 = 20000_8 = 8192_{10}$

Results

6689_{10} out of 8192_{10} were identified, see supplement.

Missing

Increasing δ

1146	2214	2217	2224	2226	2242	2250	2310	2313	2322	2374	2510	2517	2575	2630	2634	2635	2647	2656	2666	2721	
2722	2762	3006	3053	3063	3070	3102	3104	3107	3110	3116	3120	3125	3126	3127	3134	3142	3144	3151	3165	3166	
3176	3204	3205	3214	3224	3253	3266	3276	3303	3304	3305	3312	3313	3321	3322	3330	3331	3332	3334	3336	3342	
3346	3355	3364	3373	3420	3421	3423	3440	3454	3456	3457	3473	3474	3501	3502	3526	3527	3531	3532	3534	3537	
3540	3544	3545	3552	3553	3555	3556	3562	3571	3572	3574	3611	3612	3616	3620	3625	3626	3632	3633	3634	3642	
3651	3655	3656	3660	3664	3672	3677	3700	3701	3706	3715	3724	3727	3732	3744	3745	4017	4020	4033	4034	4035	
4042	4050	4066	4114	4121	4122	4123	4161	4162	4175	4177	4200	4243	4244	4245	4250	4252	4253	4276	4322	4323	
4326	4327	4331	4332	4337	4344	4346	4353	4354	4355	4364	4366	4367	4370	4371	4372	4373	4376	4402	4403	4404	
4410	4411	4412	4413	4414	4416	4417	4421	4423	4425	4426	4427	4430	4431	4436	4437	4441	4443	4446	4450	4452	
4455	4463	4464	4466	4477	4500	4504	4506	4507	4513	4515	4516	4520	4522	4524	4525	4526	4615	4616	4630	4632	
4633	4634	4644	4645	4657	4660	4661	4665	4666	4667	4670	4672	4675	4676	4677	4678	4714	4720	4722	4723	4724	
4734	4735	4736	4740	4744	4750	4753	4756	4762	4764	4765	4766	4767	4771	4774	4775	4776	5004	5005	5007	5014	
5016	5017	5021	5022	5023	5032	5033	5034	5040	5041	5042	5043	5044	5046	5047	5051	5062	5064	5065	5066	5070	
5074	5075	5114	5115	5116	5117	5120	5121	5122	5123	5124	5125	5127	5130	5131	5132	5133	5136	5141	5142	5143	
5144	5145	5146	5147	5154	5155	5156	5157	5162	5163	5165	5172	5173	5174	5175	5176	5202	5203	5204	5205	5210	
5212	5213	5214	5220	5221	5222	5223	5224	5230	5231	5232	5233	5235	5236	5237	5240	5241	5246	5247	5250	5251	
5253	5254	5260	5262	5270	5271	5272	5274	5300	5301	5307	5314	5316	5317	5320	5322	5326	5331	5340	5341	5343	
5344	5345	5355	5356	5362	5401	5402	5403	5406	5410	5411	5413	5416	5417	5420	5421	5422	5424	5425	5426	5427	
5431	5433	5434	5435	5436	5440	5443	5444	5445	5446	5453	5455	5461	5462	5464	5465	5467	5470	5501	5502	5503	
5510	5511	5516	5517	5520	5524	5525	5526	5527	5537	5541	5542	5546	5547	5557	5560	5561	5562	5563	5564	5567	
5576	5611	5615	5616	5617	5621	5622	5626	5634	5635	5650	5651	5652	5657	5660	5671	5701	5703	5704	5705	5716	
5741	5755	5756	5757	6021	6022	6023	6076	6104	6105	6106	6110	6111	6113	6114	6120	6121	6123	6142	6145	6146	
6150	6157	6160	6203	6204	6211	6213	6214	6216	6217	6220	6221	6222	6226	6227	6231	6232	6235	6237	6240	6252	
6253	6254	6262	6263	6264	6265	6266	6270	6271	6272	6274	6275	6300	6301	6302	6303	6304	6306	6307	6310	6316	
6317	6320	6321	6322	6324	6326	6334	6335	6336	6337	6340	6350	6352	6353	6354	6357	6360	6361	6362	6364	6365	
6370	6371	6372	6373	6374	6376	6401	6402	6403	6404	6405	6406	6407	6410	6412	6416	6417	6420	6421	6422	6423	
6424	6425	6426	6427	6430	6435	6436	6445	6446	6450	6451	6453	6454	6455	6461	6462	6463	6465	6467	6471	6472	
6473	6474	6475	6477	6500	6502	6504	6505	6506	6507	6510	6514	6515	6516	6517	6520	6524	6525	6526	6527	6530	
6531	6532	6533	6535	6536	6540	6541	6542	6543	6544	6546	6547	6550	6551	6552	6553	6554	6557	6560	6561	6562	
6565	6566	6567	6570	6571	6572	6574	6575	6576	6577	6604	6605	6606	6607	6610	6612	6613	6614	6615	6617	6620	
6621	6622	6623	6624	6625	6626	6630	6631	6632	6633	6634	6635	6637	6643	6644	6646	6647	6650	6651	6652	6653	
6655	6661	6662	6663	6664	6665	6670	6671	6675	6676	6702	6704	6706	6713	6714	6715	6716	6720	6721	6722	6723	
6725	6727	6730	6731	6732	6733	6734	6737	6740	6741	6742	6743	6745	6746	6747	6751	6754	6756	6757	6760	6772	
6773	6774	7006	7010	7014	7021	7023	7024	7026	7030	7040	7041	7042	7044	7045	7047	7050	7060	7062	7063	7064	
7065	7066	7073	7074	7076	7100	7101	7102	7103	7107	7110	7111	7112	7114	7120	7121	7123	7127	7130	7132	7133	
7134	7135	7137	7141	7146	7150	7154	7155	7156	7162	7163	7164	7165	7166	7170	7172	7177	7203	7214	7231	7241	
7242	7243	7244	7250	7251	7252	7253	7255	7256	7257	7261	7262	7264	7266	7270	7271	7272	7273	7300	7301	7302	
7306	7307	7310	7311	7315	7317	7320	7324	7326	7332	7345	7346	7347	7353	7357	7364	7365	7366	7367	7374	7375	
7376	7400	7402	7404	7405	7420	7422	7423	7424	7434	7435	7440	7443	7450	7451	7452	7453	7454	7462	7463	7464	
7465	7466	7467	7470	7471	7472	7473	7477	7506	7507	7510	7514	7515	7516	7521	7522	7524	7525	7526	7531	7532	
7533	7534	7540	7541	7542	7543	7545	7546	7547	7550	7551	7552	7560	7562	7563	7564	7565	7566	7572	7574	7575	
7576	7577	7600	7601	7602	7604	7605	7606	7610	7612	7613	7614	7615	7622	7623	7624	7627	7636	7642	7652	7653	
7654	7656	7665	7666	7670	7672	7701	7702	7706	7735	7736	7744										

Decreasing δ

1451	1467	1640	2250	2502	2510	2546	2547	2550	2554	2555	2567	2605	2613	2730	2763	2770	3011	3024	3044	3053	
3120	3125	3126	3127	3135	3136	3142	3143	3164	3172	3174	3331	3332	3337	3340	3350	3351	3355	3363	3364	3366	
3367	3373	3375	3377	3412	3413	3431	3432	3562	3753	3754	3762	3764	3767	3771	3772	3773	4024	4025	4027	4031	
4033	4034	4042	4050	4051	4060	4147	4150	4215	4260	4264	4266	4276	4302	4306	4323	4332	4357	4362	4363	4372	
4403	4404	4413	4414	4416	4420	4421	4423	4426	4431	4432	4435	4437	4441	4455	4462	4466	4470	4471	4474	4504	
4512	4513	4526	4564	4570	4571	4600	4601	4602	4617	4623	4625	4626	4627	4633	4636	4642	4644	4650	4670	4706	
4715	4724	4744	4750	4752	4774	4776	5004	5005	5006	5010	5013	5014	5052	5065	5067	5070	5071	5073	5074	5075	
5076	5077	5100	5102	5105	5106	5107	5115	5116	5120	5121	5122	5124	5125	5130	5131	5133	5135	5136	5137	5140	
5142	5143	5150	5156	5160	5161	5163	5164	5173	5174	5175	5176	5177	5201	5202	5213	5214	5222	5223	5231	5233	
5310	5312	5314	5316	5317	5321	5322	5326	5327	5330	5331	5332	5336	5337	5340	5341	5342	5353	5354	5355	5356	
5364	5365	5373	5374	5402	5403	5410	5417	5420	5421	5424	5425	5426	5427	5435	5436	5451	5452	5457	5460	5461	
5464	5465	5467	5470	5472	5473	5474	5476	5477	5502	5506	5507	5510	5511	5512	5514	5515	5516	5526	5532	5546	
5550	5560	5561	5562	5567	5604	5605	5606	5607	5610	5614	5615	5617	5625	5626	5643	5644	5650	5651	5704	5705	
5723	5724	5731	5740	5744	5746	5750	5751	5752	5756	5760	5761	5771	5774	5777	6000	6001	6002	6003	6004	6006	
6007	6011	6015	6022	6023	6024	6025	6040	6053	6054	6076	6105	6110	6112	6120	6121	6122	6123	6124	6126	6130	
6134	6135	6141	6142	6150	6157	6171	6172	6173	6175	6200	6201	6202	6203	6204	6206	6207	6210	6211	6212	6213	
6214	6216	6217	6221	6222	6226	6227	6231	6233	6234	6235	6236	6237	6240	6243	6244	6245	6246	6247	6254	6255	
6256	6263	6264	6265	6266	6272	6273	6274	6275	6276	6301	6303	6304	6305	6306	6307	6310	6311	6312	6313	6314	
6315	6321	6330	6337	6340	6341	6343															

Discussion

The “first integers that can not be sequentially represented under the defined operations” were identified “through brute force search” by Tim Wylie¹⁶ and published on arXiv:

Base	Increasing	Decreasing	Neither
3	0	0	0
4	13	11	16
5	27	17	27
6	67	77	92
7	260	262	292
8	614	809	1192
9	3293	4570	5414
10	10958	14324	21212

Tim Wylie¹⁶ allowed “negation of an expression” during brute force search, while authors focused on “genuine crazy sequential representations”, which by definition do not allow “negation of an expression”. Nevertheless, identical “first integers” were identified:

Base	Increasing	Decreasing	Neither
8	$1146_8 = 614_{10}$	$1451_8 = 809_{10}$	$2250_8 = 1192_{10}$

Note

Authors consider base 8 crazy sequential representations to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial. Authors did not simplify and/or optimize the crazy sequential representations.

Authors do not guaranty:

- Published crazy sequential representations are the shortest in existence.
- Published crazy sequential representations are in their simplest form.
- Unavailable crazy sequential representations do not exists.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530982>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
22. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546991>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530984>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
23. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7564973>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2536047>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 09 Jan 2019
24. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7547423>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/10.5281/zenodo.2531777>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFFF)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
25. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7639799>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2551565>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (03)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 28 Jan 2019
26. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7619648>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2547763>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to ####)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 23 Jan 2019
27. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7665629>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555620>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to ####)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Saturday 02 Feb 2019
28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2543626>
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000
Inder J. Taneja. Monday 18 Jan 2019
29. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2556036>
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20000 to 30000
Inder J. Taneja. Sunday 03 Feb 2019

30. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7683572>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2558454>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (04)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 06 Feb 2019
31. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7689386>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2559524>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (05)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Thursday 07 Feb 2019
32. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7713548>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2563944>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 9 (0000 up to 8888)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 13 Feb 2019
33. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7731674>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2571496>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 8 (0000 up to 7777)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 18 Feb 2019
34. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7731677>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2571500>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 7 (0000 up to 6666)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 18 Feb 2019